

Innovative experiences and perspectives in swine reproduction
Experiencias y perspectivas innovadoras en la reproducción porcina

17th INTERNATIONAL TECHNICAL MEETING OF SPECIALISTS IN SWINE REPRODUCTION

17º ENCUENTRO TÉCNICO INTERNACIONAL DE ESPECIALISTAS EN REPRODUCCIÓN PORCINA

MAY 14 - 15, 2025

WORLD TRADE CENTER
ZARAGOZA - SPAIN

09:15

OPENING
INAUGURACIÓN

Jorge Azcón
President Aragon Government
Jesús Mena
Magapor General Manager
Raquel Ausejo
Magapor Technical Manager

MANUEL ÁLVAREZ

Receptors and channels in spermatozoa: fertility biomarkers?
Receptores y canales en espermatozoides: ¿biomarcadores de fertilidad?

IOANNIS TSAKMAKIDIS

Potential impact of biomedical techniques on the progression of boar fertility predicting methods
Impacto potencial de las técnicas biomédicas en la progresión de los métodos de predicción de la fertilidad del verraco

ANDREA CLIMENTE

Follow-up and quality control analysis plan for seminal doses received at Magapor 2024
Plan de Seguimiento y análisis de control de calidad de dosis seminales recibidas en Magapor 2024

11:15

COFFEE BREAK
PAUSA PARA CAFÉ

Poster presentations

HORACIO GABOSI

Actualización tecnológica de un centro de verracos en Argentina - Los motivos
Actualización tecnológica de un centro de verracos en Argentina - Los motivos

MICHAEL AKSEL ELLERMANN

Extender trial results and relationship between semen age and farm performance

Resultados de ensayos de diluyentes y relación entre la edad del semen y el rendimiento en granja

ALBERTO ALFONSO

How to lead production and sustainability. The Mexican example

Cómo liderar la producción y sostenibilidad. El ejemplo mexicano

13:50

LUNCH
COMIDA

World Trade Center

15:30

MEGAN HOOD

Challenges at boar studs and possible solutions

Desafíos en los centros de inseminación y posibles soluciones

ROUND TABLE
MESA REDONDA

Bandas de cinco semanas y su repercusión en el CIA.
Bandas de cinco semanas y su repercusión en el CIA.

VÍCTOR VISTUÉ
NACHO TARDÍO
RUBÉN CALVO
PAULA SÁNCHEZ

Magapor provides simultaneous translation / Magapor proporciona traducción simultánea

09:15

● RAFAEL **KUMMER**

Managing and feeding the modern sow: Brazilian industry perspective

Manejo y alimentación de la cerda moderna: perspectiva de la industria brasileña

● MICHAEL AKSEL **ELLERMANN**

Hemoglobin level in weaned pigs

Nivel de hemoglobina en cerdos destetados

10:50

○ **COFFEE BREAK**

PAUSA PARA CAFÉ

● GUILLERMO **RAMIS**

Circadian rhythms in pigs: much to learn

Ritmos circadianos en cerdos: mucho por aprender

● CARLES **VILALTA**

Global PRRS situation: eradication is possible

Situación mundial del PRRS: la erradicación es posible

● LUIS **VARONA**

Genetic improvement of pig breeding: fertility, litter size and piglet viability

Mejora genética de la reproducción porcina: fertilidad, tamaño de camada y viabilidad de los lechones

13:30

○ **CLOSING**

CLAUSURA

María Victoria Falceto

Director of Magapor Professorship (Unizar)

Jesús Mena

Magapor General Manager

Raquel Ausejo

Magapor Technical Manager

Magapor provides simultaneous translation

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Evaluation of the effect of different boar lines on the productive efficiency of their offspring

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1. Introduction

Genetic improvement in pig production plays a pivotal role in optimizing performance and feed efficiency. This study focuses on comparing different finishing boar lines based on Pietrain line, renowned for their high lean meat percentage and carcass yield (Sellier et al., 1991). The objective is to evaluate the impact of these genetic lines on various productive parameters to identify the most efficient option for intensive fattening systems.

The Pietrain breed has long been valued for its superior muscle development and feed conversion efficiency. (Font iFurnols, *et al.*, 2005) However, variations exist among different genetic lines, which can significantly influence growth rates, feed intake, and carcass quality. Understanding these differences is crucial for producers aiming to align genetic selection with their specific production goals: whether prioritizing rapid growth, feed efficiency, or meat quality.

2. Materials and Methods

Four experimental groups were established based on the genetic line of the semen dose used (Lines A, B, C, and D). Each group consisted of 25–30 inseminated sows, with an initial sample size of 310–380 animals per treatment. This design ensured robust statistical comparisons across the groups.

Key parameters measured during transition phase included:

- Initial weight
- Final transition weight
- Average daily gain (ADG)

During the fattening Phase, animals were weighed up to five times, and feed intake per pen was recorded to calculate:

- Average daily gain (ADG)
- Average daily feed intake (ADFI)
- Feed conversion ratio (FCR)

At the slaughterhouse, carcass yield and lean meat composition were assessed using the Autofom system, ensuring precise and objective measurements.

Data were analyzed using ANOVA, followed by Tukey's post-hoc tests for multiple comparisons. Multiple regression analysis was also employed to explore relationships between genetic lines and productive outcomes.

3. Results

The study revealed significant differences among the genetic lines:

- **Line C** demonstrated the highest standardized ADG (1030 g/day) and ADFI (1.84 kg/day). However, it exhibited a lower lean meat percentage (62.7%) compared to other lines. This suggests that while Line C excels in growth performance, it may compromise carcass quality.
- **Line D** showed outstanding growth during the transition phase (326 g/day), indicating strong early-stage performance. This line could be particularly advantageous for systems focusing on rapid early growth.
- **Line A and B** achieved a higher lean meat percentage (63.8%), making them ideal for producers targeting premium carcass quality. However, these lines underperformed in fattening phase metrics, such as ADG and FCR, highlighting a trade-off between meat quality and growth efficiency.

These findings underscore the importance of aligning genetic selection with specific production objectives.

4. Conclusions

The choice of boar line should be tailored to the farm's production goals:

- **For maximizing weight and growth: Line C** is the optimal choice due to its superior ADG and ADFI.
- **For premium carcass quality: Line A and B** are preferable, despite their lower growth rates.
- **For balanced performance: Line D** offers moderate growth, particularly excelling in early phases.

Ultimately, the decision depends on whether the priority is feed efficiency, final weight, or meat quality. This study provides valuable insights for producers to make informed genetic selections that align with their operational priorities.

5. References

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Serum pooling: making PRRSV surveillance in the boar stud affordable

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Introduction

Porcine Reproductive and Respiratory Syndrome has become one of the most important diseases in intensive pig production worldwide. Semen from PRRSV-infected boars can transmit the virus to negative sows inseminated (Rovira et al. 2007). Due to that, European regulation trends are focused on PRRS surveillance (Delegated Regulation (EU) 2020/686 December 17, 2019). Therefore, a frequent monitoring program to confirm the PRRSV-free status of the boar stud, is key to avoiding the dissemination of the disease. Different matrices have been proposed to monitor PRRSV, although serum is still considered the golden standard. One strategy to reduce the cost of these monitoring protocols is pooling serum samples. Nevertheless, pooling may reduce the individual sensitivity of the RT-PCR test (Rovira et al. 2007).

This study aimed to evaluate the detection limit of pooling RT-PCR PRRSV-positive serums with different levels of viremia.

Material and methods

Sample selection

RT-PCR PRRSV type 1 positive samples were obtained from HIPRA DIAGNOS. The pooling and dilution effect was assessed as shown in figure 1. Positive samples were categorized into the following Ct range groups: 18-25, 25-30, 30-35, and 35-38.

Fig. 1. Dilution protocol simulating the pooling of one positive serum within pools of 5, 10, 30, 60 and 120 serums

RNA extraction and RT-PCR

Viral RNA extraction and RT-PCR testing was conducted using a commercial Kit (MagMAX™ CORE Nucleic Acid Purification Kit, and The VetMAX™ PRRSV EU & NA 3.0 Kit), both following the manufacturer's instructions. Only samples ≤ 38 were considered positive.

Statistical analysis

Sensitivity was defined as the probability of a sample testing positive, given that one of the samples contained in each group was truly positive. Diagnostic sensitivity was estimated for total and each Ct group at each pool size. The 95% confidence intervals were calculated using the Clopper-Pearson method. Data analysis was performed using R software (version 4.4.1, R Core Team).

Results

Group	Pool Size				
	5	10	30	60	120
18-25	100% 14/14 (77-100)				
25-30	100% 11/11 (72-100)				
30-35	100% 13/13 (75-100)	84.6% 11/13 (75-100)	76.92% 10/13 (46-95)	38.46% 6/13 (19-75)	38.46% 5/13 (14-68)
35-38	66.67% 6/9 (30-93)	22.22% 2/9 (3-60)	11.11% 1/9 (0-48)	11.11% 1/9 (0-48)	11.11% 1/9 (0-48)
Total	93.6% 44/47 (82-99)	80.9% 38/47 (67-91)	76.7% 36/47 (62-88)	68.0% 32/47 (53-81)	65.9% 31/47 (51-79)

Table 1. Sensitivity (%) by RT-PCR CT group and dilution, number of positive samples out of the total per group, and 95% confidence interval. Colour code: green for sensitivity >90%, yellow for sensitivity 60-90%, orange for 30-60, and red for sensitivity <30%.

The results are summarized in Table 1. All the pools from the 18-25 and 25-30 Ct groups tested PRRSV positive for all the pooling processes (sensitivities of 100%). On the other hand, samples from the 30-35 and 35-38 Ct groups had a decrease in sensitivity whilst increasing the pool size.

Discussion

Understanding the effect of pooling on RT-PCR PRRSV positive samples is key to implementing an effective surveillance strategy. Results from this study confirm that pooling at least 5 serums has either no effect on sensitivity on serums with Ct values below 35, or a moderate effect on Ct values between 35 to 38.

These results are consistent with Rovira et al. (2007), where the sensitivity for pooling five serum samples varied from 6% at 1-day post-infection to 100% at 12 days post-infection. This indicates that the sensitivity of pooled samples depends on the viral load of the positive sample. Considering that infection with PRRSV isolates results in a high viral load in serum, especially in seronegative animals, pooling can be a valid strategy to reduce cost and still detect the early onset of the disease in a boar stud. For instance, the viral load in serum was between 10^3 and 10^5 Log RNA copies/ml after 3 and 5 days post the experimental infection with a low virulence PRRSV type 2 strain (Rovira et al. 2007).

Pooling is widely used, as it reduces monitoring costs. It allows testing a large number of animals with fewer tests, thus lowering testing expenses. The estimated cost of individual PRRSV surveillance testing per 60 ml dose is close to 5.19% of the total cost of a seminal dose, around 25-30 euros per test. This is the third most significant cost after fixed costs (workers' salaries, energy, facilities, etc.) and variable costs (feed, medication and sawdust). Looking specifically at the surveillance cost per dose, this could be potentially reduced to 0.17% based on an extreme monitoring strategy, pooling up to 120 samples, compared with the individual cost. However, given the importance of avoiding false-negative results and considering the worst-case scenario, a surveillance strategy based on testing serum in pools of five would reduce costs from 5.19% to 1.04% (calculated from Luongo et al. 2022), while sensitivity would decrease from 100% to 93.6% based on the results considering all the levels of viremia.

Additionally, pooling allows us to monitor more animals, compensating for the individual decrease in sensitivity. This approach could be particularly valuable in cases of low disease prevalence.

Conclusion

In conclusion, PRRSV surveillance in boar studs is crucial. While serum is the most sensitive sample for detection, monitoring protocols became a significant cost, affecting the boar studs' efficiency. Strategies such as sample pooling help to reduce costs without compromising significantly the sensitivity, especially in high viral load scenarios. However, it is critical to balance the pros and cons, ensuring the effectiveness of early virus detection.

References

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Luongo C, Llamas-López PJ, Hernández-Caravaca I, Matás C, García-Vázquez FA. *Should all fractions of the boar ejaculate be prepared for insemination rather than using the sperm-rich only?* *Biology* 2022; 11:210.

Reduction of confinement time in pregnant sows, improvement of animal welfare and production parameters

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INTRODUCTION

Modern pig farming has had to adapt to current consumer demands and new genetics that require different treatments and the handling of our pigs.

The search for strategies that allow improving animal welfare must be adapted to the facilities we have and try to ensure that we can obtain a productive benefit and therefore, be compensated financially.

We know that improved welfare will improve the production of our animals. Since 2013, legislation has restricted the time a sow can be in an individual stall to 28 days post-service. The reason is the stress produced by fights during the establishment of the hierarchy does not cause embryonic reabsorption, since there has been time for the embryos to implant (10-12 days of gestation) and the gestation is more advanced, reducing the risk of possible early pregnancy losses.

Our aim is to improve the welfare of sows with the “Cover and Release” management affecting the productive results of the farm.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A commercial breeding farm with a census of 1000 sows, weaned at 28 days, positive and stable for PRRSv, and negative for dysentery, rhinitis, and *Actinobacillus pleuropneumoniae*.

We created two groups of sows from which we collected reproductive data for 12 weeks, changing only the following management conditions between both groups:

- “Cover and Release” group: These sows only remain in the box from the day of weaning until about 3-4 days after the last mating, then are housed in a group.
- Control group: The sows remain in their mating cages until 28 days after insemination as required by law.

ANIMAL MANAGEMENT AND FEEDING

From the day after weaning, each sow will be fed 3.5 kg of gestation feed until she comes into heat. We will reduce the feed during mating and return to high levels during the first third of gestation. In the second and third we will maintain low levels of feed until farrowing.

The sows will be placed in groups of 20 animals once they are released and feed will be provided once a day in the morning. In both groups, the first two days after release we will give high levels of feed to avoid fights over it.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The database is analyzed with two statistical tests: Shapiro-Wilk and Student's T test.

1. Normality test (Shapiro-Wilk):

- Statistics = 0.944
- p-value = 0.557

The differences between the rows follow a normal distribution ($p > 0.05$).

2. Paired samples t- test:

- Statistics = - 0.735
- p-value = 0.478

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Graph 1. % of fertility in the "Cover and Release" group.

Graph 2. % of fertility in the Control group (stay in box until 28 days of gestation).

As we can see in the fertility data, in the data from the “Cover and Release” Group, fertility does not worsen, it even seems to remain more stable over time.

The feeding curve that we propose to increase the consumption of sows after weaning aims, on the one hand, to have a strong filling of the mammary gland and to produce its drying. On the other hand, to have a good growth of the preovulatory corpus luteum, taking into account that the sows at the time of covering will reduce their consumption due to the increase in estrogen. These high levels of feed will be maintained in the first third of gestation to ensure that progesterone levels remain high and provide the uterus with the appropriate conditions for the implantation of the embryos to occur.

Regarding the management of nutrition in early pregnancy, the paradigm that increased nutrition in the first third of pregnancy causes a clearance of systemic progesterone by increasing the feeding pattern must be contradicted. We now know that we have not only systemic progesterone, but a progesterone that goes directly from the ovary to the uterus, that acts locally and is not subject to hepatic clearance.

Increasing the amount of feed in the first third of gestation provides us with important advantages, such as an increase in the amount of progesterone, since during the first 12 days the amount of luteal tissue is independent of the luteinizing hormone and is more correlated with insulin and other hormones. Therefore, an increase in feed is positive to improve irrigation and, therefore, the quality of the placenta. This will have an impact on the size of the piglets at birth.

If in this early phase of gestation there is a reduction in feed consumption due to increased competition or deficit, there will be a loss of embryos that will lead to a return to estrus, or a reduction in litter size.

As for prolificacy, the study is carried out on total births without counting mummified ones, although stillbirths are included.

Graph 3. Total births in the "Cover and Release" group.

Graph 4. Total births in the "Control" group.

Statistical analysis: No statistically significant differences were observed.

CONCLUSION

We can say that implementing this management strategy that improves animal welfare, together with a feeding pattern that we believe helps maintain good gestation, did not worsen fertility data in our production.

In both groups, the same feeding system was used with the same amounts of total feed, administering more in early gestation and then maintaining a flat feeding curve.

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3. Hazeleger W, Soede NM, Kemp B. The effect of feeding strategy during the pre-follicular phase on subsequent follicular development in the pig. *Domest Anim Endocrinol.* 2005 Aug;29(2):362-70. doi: 10.1016/j.domaniend.2005.03.007. Epub 2005 Apr 22. PMID: 15878256.

Evaluation of Swim-Up Capacitation in Frozen-Thawed Boar Sperm Using the CASA Magavision System

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Introduction

Computer-assisted sperm analysis (CASA) systems are essential tools for accurate and consistent assessment of semen parameters (Yániz et al., 2018). Their use in artificial insemination (AI) centers has optimized sperm quality control and evaluation processes. In recent years, technological advances have enhanced CASA systems by incorporating improved analysis algorithms, artificial intelligence for image processing, and automated procedures. These developments have enabled more comprehensive and objective evaluations of sperm motility and morphology.

The Magavision system is specifically designed for AI centers, allowing the evaluation of diluted and refrigerated porcine semen samples (Ausejo-Marcos et al., 2024). However, there is limited information on its use to evaluate frozen-thawed sperm samples and their behavior after capacitation procedures, which are critical for in vitro fertilization (IVF) procedures.

The aim of this study was to evaluate frozen-thawed porcine semen samples before and after capacitation using the swim-up technique. Various sperm parameters were analyzed using the CASA Magavision system, focusing on motility and morphology.

Materials and Methods

Frozen-thawed semen samples from a fertile boar were used. The 0.25 ml straws stored in liquid nitrogen were thawed in a water bath at 38°C for 30 seconds. The sample was diluted with 2 ml of PIG-SUM sperm swim-up medium (Embryocloud, Murcia, Spain) pre-warmed at 38 °C. Sperm selection was performed by adding 1 ml of PIG-SUM media in a conical tube and 1 ml of thawed diluted sperm to the bottom of the tube. The tubes were then incubated (38°C, 20 min, 45° angle) and 500 µL of the upper medium was aspirated (Navarro-Serna et al., 2021). Semen samples were analyzed before and after the sperm selection using the CASA Magavision system (Magapor, Spain) and a microscope equipped with a ×10 negative phase-contrast objective.

Data were analyzed by non-parametric U de Mann-Whitney test using SPSS v 28 statistical software, comparing pre- and post-swim-up values. Differences were considered significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

The results revealed that while some parameters, such as total and progressive motility, did not show significant differences after the swim-up process ($p > 0.05$), other indicators showed notable changes.

In particular, the percentage of slow spermatozoa decreased significantly ($p = 0.013$), suggesting an effective selection of spermatozoa with improved motility. Similarly, the presence of abnormal morphology, such as 'folded tail' and 'coiled tail', decreased significantly ($p = 0.019$ and $p = 0.013$, respectively), which may be related to the removal of structurally defective spermatozoa during the swim-up process.

In addition, certain kinematic parameters increased significantly after capacitation, including DCL ($p = 0.003$), DAP ($p = 0.008$), DSL ($p = 0.040$), VCL ($p = 0.019$), VAP ($p = 0.040$), and ALH ($p = 0.008$). These changes reflect an improvement in sperm motility and velocity, which may correlate with improved fertilization potential. Conversely, parameters such as LIN ($p = 0.005$) and STR ($p = 0.040$) decreased significantly, suggesting reduced linearity in sperm trajectory after capacitation. This phenomenon may be related to changes in flagellar function in preparation for fertilization.

Conclusion

The CASA Magavision system effectively detected significant changes in sperm parameters after capacitation by swim-up, confirming its utility in the evaluation of frozen-thawed sperm. These findings may have important implications for optimizing sperm selection protocols in reproductive biotechnologies such as IVF and the production of high-quality embryos.

References

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- Yániz, J.L., Silvestre, M.A., Santolaria, P., Soler, C., 2018. CASA-Mot in mammals: an update. *Reprod. Fertil. Dev.* 30, 799-809.

Parameter	Pre-Swim-Up	Post-Swim-Up	p-Value
Total Motility (%)	24.87 ± 1.80	25.01 ± 3.40	0.859
Progressive Motility (%)	20.87 ± 1.36	19.86 ± 3.50	0.440
Motile and Normal (%)	15.60 ± 1.02	15.64 ± 3.05	0.513
Static Sperm (%)	75.13 ± 1.80	74.99 ± 3.40	0.859
Slow Sperm (%)	5.36 ± 0.72	2.34 ± 0.61	0.013*
Medium-Speed Sperm (%)	7.17 ± 0.94	4.70 ± 0.62	0.075
Rapid Sperm (%)	12.34 ± 1.91	17.96 ± 4.33	0.310
Total Abnormal Forms (%)	35.54 ± 0.99	31.63 ± 3.60	0.165
Folded Tail (%)	2.75 ± 0.30	1.64 ± 0.26	0.019*
Coiled Tail (%)	0.57 ± 0.19	0.00 ± 0.00	0.013*
DCL (µm)	102.74 ± 7.04	146.37 ± 9.73	0.003*
DAP (µm)	69.78 ± 5.13	94.65 ± 5.88	0.008*
DSL (µm)	56.17 ± 3.31	70.00 ± 4.84	0.040*
VCL (µm/s)	124.64 ± 12.34	209.20 ± 40.83	0.019*
VAP (µm/s)	86.89 ± 10.14	144.27 ± 34.44	0.040*
ALH (µm)	7.69 ± 0.38	10.73 ± 0.89	0.008*
LIN (%)	56.34 ± 1.99	49.19 ± 1.20	0.005*
STR (%)	81.76 ± 1.92	74.39 ± 1.72	0.040*

(* p < 0.05, statistically significant differences)

Evaluation of colostrum and milk composition according to sow parity and body condition prior farrowing using different techniques

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Introduction.

Colostrum and milk intake are critical for piglet survivability during lactation period. The colostrum and milk composition can be influenced by sow parity, but the impact of sow body condition (SBC) at farrowing on it is still limited. Different techniques are used to evaluate SBC in farms, such as Caliper, measurement of backfat (BFU) or loin muscle (LMU) thickness by ultrasounds, among others. Thus, this study aimed to evaluate the effect of parity and SBC using different methods on colostrum and milk composition.

Material and Methods.

Forty-six sows with different parities were selected in a farrowing farm and were divided into three categories: Gilts (n=18), 2nd-4th (n=16) and $\geq 5^{\text{th}}$ (n=12) parity. Sow's BC was measured by Caliper, BFU and LMU a week pre-farrowing. Colostrum and milk samples of each sow were collected at farrowing and weaning, respectively. Parameters as percentage (%) of fat, protein, lactose, dry extract (DE) and urea concentration (mg/L) were evaluated in colostrum and milk. Data normal distribution was evaluated using Shapiro-Wilk test. Comparison of colostrum and milk composition between sow parity's categories were performed using ANOVA test and correlation between techniques used to evaluate BC was done by Pearson coefficient (r). Significant differences were considered when $p < 0.05$.

Results.

Gilts showed BC losses using Caliper and BFU compared to sows with $\geq 5^{\text{th}}$ parity that increased BC ($p < 0.05$). The highest correlation between methods was Caliper and BFU ($r = 0.822$), followed by Caliper with LMU ($r = 0.515$) and BFU and LMU ($r = 0.495$). Colostrum from gilts showed higher fat% than older sows ($p < 0.05$). Milk showed higher fat% and urea concentration in gilts compared to older sows, whereas gilts showed lower lactose% than other parities ($p < 0.05$). A significant negative correlation ($r = -0.352$; $p = 0.021$) in lactose% was found between colostrum and milk.

Discussion and conclusion.

Caliper could be a practical alternative for sow's BC monitorization into breeding herds according to the correlation between methods obtained in this study. Moreover, the BC losses observed in gilts could be associated with fat mobilization and thus, with the highest fat% observed in colostrum and milk in these younger sows.

Evaluation of the main pathogens involved in piglet neonatal diarrhoea and its impact in piglet's growth in 15 different breeding farms

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Background and Objectives

Neonatal diarrhea (ND) in pigs is a multifactorial disease with a significant impact on piglets during their first weeks of life. This digestive disorder increases mortality rates and reduces the average piglet daily weight gain (ADWG) at lactation period. This study aimed to determine the main etiological agents in 15 farms in Aragón (Spain) and assessing the impact of ND on the ADWG of piglets.

Materials and Methods

Fifteen ND-affected farms in Aragón (Spain) were studied. Samples from 15 piglets with ND were collected per farm (n=225). These samples were analysed for detection by PCR in pools of 5 for *E.coli*, *Clostridium perfringens* type A (CPA), *Clostridioides difficile*, *Cystoisospora (C.) suis*, Coronavirus, and Rotavirus. *E. coli* virulence factors as adhesins (F4, F41) and enterotoxins (Sta,Stb,LT) and CPA toxins (α , β -2) were also investigated. Farm 3 was selected as representative for evaluation of the impact of ND on ADWG. Piglets with ND (n=336) and without (n=461) were weighted individually at birth and weaning for ADWG calculation. Statistical significance was set as $p<0.05$.

Results

The most prevalent pathogens were *E.coli* (100%;45/45), *C.perfringens* (84.4%; 8/45), and *Clostridioides difficile* (55.6%;24/45). Regarding *E. coli* virulence factors, *Gen eae* (86.7%), Stb (71.1%) and F41 (64.4%) were the most prevalent. For CPA alpha and beta-2 toxins were detected in 80.0% of samples. Interestingly, coinfections involving up to six different pathogens were detected in three farms. All farms were negative for *C. suis*, Coronavirus and Rotavirus. In farm 3, ND group showed a significantly lower ADWG (0.171 ± 0.061 kg) compared to ND (0.188 ± 0.065 kg).

Discussion and Conclusion

The results indicated that *E. coli* and CPA are still involved in ND cases in suckling piglets on tested farms, although prophylaxis measures in sows had been implemented previously. Further studies are needed to confirm their role in ND and assess their impact on piglet growth.

Evaluation of the refractometer as a tool for assessing immunity in piglets

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INTRODUCTION

The use of hyperprolific genetic lines has increased the number of piglets born alive per sow per year. However, this increase is often associated with reduced birth weights, due to the negative correlation between litter size and fetal growth. Lower birth weights are in turn linked to decreased piglet viability and survival. Adequate colostrum intake during the first hours of life is essential to enhance piglet survival, as colostrum provides passive immunity through the transfer of immunoglobulins (Ig). Several laboratory techniques are available to monitor colostrum intake, with the immunocrit being the most widely used in swine. However, most of these techniques require specialized laboratory equipment. As a more practical and field- adapted alternative, the refractometer estimates total protein (TP) levels in serum, which correlate with Ig concentrations. The aim of this study was to evaluate passive immune transfer in piglets using both the refractometer and immunocrit techniques, and to assess the correlation between them. Additionally, the impact of freezing and thawing serum samples on TP concentrations was analyzed using the refractometer.

METHODOLOGY

Blood samples were collected via jugular venipuncture from 442 piglets with a minimum average body weight of 1 kg, 24 hours after birth. Each piglet was individually identified. The samples were centrifuged to obtain serum, and TP levels in fresh samples were measured using both the refractometer and immunocrit technique. An additional 107 piglets were randomly selected and resampled at 21 days of age to re-evaluate TP levels using the refractometer. All samples (n = 549) were then frozen at -20 °C for 7 days to assess the impact of freezing on TP measurements.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results showed a correlation coefficient of 0.35 ($p < 0.05$) between the two techniques. Using an immunocrit threshold of 0.1 to define adequate colostrum intake (Vallet et al., 2013), it was determined that 52.94% (234/442) of the piglets received an adequate transfer of passive immunity. The proportion of gamma globulins (mainly IgG) in the serum of 2-day-old piglets is approximately 36%. Extrapolating this value, and using a cut-off point of 3.4 g/dL of IgG to define adequate colostrum intake (Vallet et al., 2013), the results obtained with the refractometer indicated that 99.32% (439/442) of the piglets were inadequately colostrum-fed (TP < 3.4 g/dL). Regarding the effect of freezing, total protein (TP) concentration significantly decreased after freezing in the 21-day-old piglets ($p < 0.05$), but no significant change was observed in the samples taken at birth.

CONCLUSION

The sensitivity of the optical refractometer to identify inadequately colostrum-fed piglets was lower than that of the immunocrit, highlighting the need for further studies to establish an accurate threshold value in swine. Nevertheless, the correlation between both methods was statistically significant, suggesting that the refractometer could represent a rapid and cost- effective alternative to the immunocrit for assessing colostrum intake in piglets under field conditions.

In addition, the effect of freezing on samples measured with the refractometer was found to be dependent on total protein concentration, as a significant effect was observed at higher protein levels.

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Effect on fertility of including an omega-3 rich supplement in sows during the peri-weaning period

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Fertility is one of the most important parameters in pig production, as it directly influences farm efficiency and profitability. Good fertility allows for a greater number of piglets born per litter and reduces the interval between farrowings, maximizing the number of piglets produced per year. It also improves farm occupancy by reducing the number of unproductive sows, optimizing feed and management costs. High fertility also reduces losses associated with reproductive problems and minimizes the impact of prenatal mortality, helping to maintain a constant level of production and improving the farm's economic viability.

The use of docosahexaenoic acid (**DHA**), eicosapentaenoic acid (**EPA**), and antioxidant supplements can improve sow fertility before insemination due to a combination of positive effects on overall health, the reproductive system, and the quality of the uterine environment. They also improve oocyte quality, improving the composition of oocyte cell membranes, increasing their fluidity and functionality. This improves oocyte maturation, their ability to be fertilized, and early embryo development. On the other hand, Omega 3 reduces inflammation, because it is precursor to molecules such as resolvins and protectins. A uterine environment with less inflammation is more favorable for embryo implantation and early pregnancy development. Also, omega-3 fatty acids compete with omega-6 fatty acids in prostaglandin synthesis. Omega-3-derived prostaglandins (such as PGE3) are less proinflammatory than omega-6-derived prostaglandins (such as PGE2).

This balance contributes to better regulation of the reproductive cycle and the implantation process. Improved uterine blood flow. Omega-3s improve blood vessel elasticity and reduce platelet aggregation. Furthermore, it increases blood flow to the uterus and ovaries, promoting implantation and maintaining pregnancy. This effect protects oocytes and the early embryo from damage caused by oxidative stress. In addition, the supplement of Omega-3 fatty acids influences the composition of follicular fluid, the medium where oocytes develop in the ovaries.

A follicular fluid rich in omega-3 creates an optimal metabolic environment for oocyte maturation. In this study are 3 trials of the efficacy of using a nutritional supplement (**Ω3-RS**) which include omega-3 fatty acids plus antioxidants, during the peri-weaning period on three different farms with different genetics. The objective of these 3 trials was to determine the effect on fertility evaluated by echography of including **Ω3-RS** in the diets of pregnant sows.

In these trials, a dose of 70 grams per sow/day was used for 7 days before mating, starting in the last days of lactation. In the case of gilts, it is offered 7 days after insemination, except in gilts with heat programming, where it could be applied similarly to multiparous sows. Fertility was calculated after pregnancy diagnosis by ultrasound sonde (MAGASCAN; Magapor, Zaragoza, Spain), 28 days post-breeding.

Trial 1 was conducted on a Phase 1 pig farm with a capacity of 1,800 sows with weekly production batches. The genetic was LDxLW (Danbred) crossed with Pietrain (German origin). The trial was conducted for 35 weeks (from December 2023 to August 2024), with a total of 2,635 matings. From week 1 to week 11 of the trial, sows were fed a control diet. From then until the end of the trial (week 35), sows were fed the same basal diet supplemented with Ω3-RS. Sows in the Ω3-RS group had higher fertility than those in the control group (92.2% vs. 85.0%; $P < 0.001$). This improvement is also greater if we only compare data from the same time of year. Also, this positive effect is also observed in both primiparous and multiparous sows (6.6 and 7.2% of improvement, respectively).

Trial 2. The trial was conducted on a Phase 1 farm with a capacity of 500 sows in 3-week production batches. The herd's genetics are LDxLW (Topigs) crossed with Duroc. The trial was conducted over 10 bands (from March to October 2024), with a target of 80 matings per band. Sows fed with the Ω3-RS diet tended to have higher fertility than those in the control group (2.5% vs. 85.1%; $P = 0.077$). This is an 8.7% difference compared to the fertility of the control group (7.4% increase basis points).

Trial 3. The trial was conducted on a closed-cycle pig farm with a capacity for 1,000 sows in weekly batches. The farm's genetics are Iberian-Duroc crossbred. The trial was conducted over 16 weekly batches (from week 33 to 48 of 2024) with a total of 862 matings. Sows were fed with the same Control feed all the trial, except from 41 to 42 wk, where the diet was supplemented with Ω3-RS.

Sows fed with the Ω 3-RS diet showed higher fertility than the two control groups (82.2% vs. 72.2% and 74.7%, for Control 1 and Control 2, respectively). The fertility improvement is 12.1% in the Ω 3-RS group compared to the two controls as an average.

In conclusion, the use of Omega-3 rich supplement during the peri-weaning period increased ultrasound fertility in all three farms (9.3%, 8.5%, and 12.1%).

Key words: fertility, omega-3, pregnant sows, ultrasound

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